

CPTED Review of Development Applications

Dr Terence Love
CEO Design Out Crime and CPTED Centre

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Many jurisdictions worldwide require CPTED review of Development Applications (DAs) and infrastructure development as part of the approval process.

In Australia, the accepted qualifications for review of DAs and large infrastructure are:

- International CPTED Association (**ICA Certified CPTED Professional**) for large complex developments (e.g. large retail/residential; large transport hubs/rail stations; government complexes; large educational complexes; sports stadium complexes, CPTED in counter-terrorism)
- **NSW Safer by Design 5-day CPTED training certificate** (currently only available for Police) for large complex developments (e.g. large retail/residential; large transport hubs/rail stations; government complexes; large educational complexes; CPTED in counter-terrorism).

- International CPTED Association (**ICA Certified CPTED Practitioner** for smaller single-use developments (e.g. houses, schools; small shopping centres; public squares; parks, residential blocks; bus stops; small train stations)

Each of the above qualifications requires the participant to:

- Be an experienced professional in security, urban design, architecture, community development or policing
- Have undertaken 40 hours of approved CPTED training
- Have demonstrated experience as a team member undertaking CPTED review and writing an approved CPTED report for one or more real-world situations.

The International CPTED standard that applies to undertaking CPTED review of development applications is **ISO:22342:2021** with its 10 CPTED methods (4 social and 6 physical) and its three CPTED processes (for design, planning and site management). ISO 22341:2021 is worldwide replacing the many older CPTED, 'Design Out Crime', 'Safer Design' and similar CPTED guidelines and handbooks. The primary change is the international ISO 22341:2021 CPTED standard is based on up-to-date evidence. Copies of ISO22341:2021 are available from the usual standards suppliers.

The International CPTED Association Class-A and Class-B CPTED training is only delivered by trainers certified by the ICA and who are already ICA-certified CPTED Professionals. **Class-A certified CPTED courses** cover all the formal training requirements for the (**ICA Certified CPTED Practitioner** certification. An additional short course (along with more experience) is required to upgrade to **ICA Certified CPTED Professional** .

Here at the [Design Out Crime and CPTED Centre](#), we provide **in-person and online ICA Class-A CPTED training** along with **advanced CPTED training**, and custom CPTED training for specific groups and purposes.

Our next [certified Class-A in-person CPTED Training will be held in Perth 18-22nd November](#).

Please see www.designoutcrime.org for details of current CPTED training or contact me directly to discuss your needs (t.love@designoutcrime.org Tel: 61434975848).

Background

Dr Terence Love is CEO of the **Design Out Crime and CPTED Centre**, which provides the following services in Australia and internationally:

- Certified Crime Prevention Through Environmental Design (CPTED) training to professionals in Police, Planning, Architecture, Security, Community Safety and related fields.
- CPTED reviews of development applications (over \$13 billion of projects to date)
- Advising and writing on national and international CPTED standards and guidebooks
- Providing crime prevention advice to Police, governments, infrastructure developers and planners, architects and related professionals
- Undertaking and publishing cutting-edge research for more than 25 years
- Developing improved crime prevention theories and strategies